

A Candidate Item Pool for Narrative Clarity, Story-Content Coherence, and Engagement in Interactive-Fiction Learning Scenarios

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Abstract

This note documents a candidate item pool for the perceived quality of interactive-fiction (IF) learning scenarios. The pool comprises nine Likert items covering three constructs: narrative clarity, story-content coherence, and engagement. Items were adapted from four established instruments (NES, TS-SF, IMI, MEEGA+) and complemented by two new items written to capture the intrinsic-integration principle. The pool is designed for descriptive use in short online pilot studies within the IF learning domain. Adapting items from validated instruments is a reasonable and documented approach for this purpose. The pool should be read as an early-stage candidate item set, not as a confirmed measurement scale.

1 Motivation

Interactive fiction can carry educational content in short branching scenarios. Whether such a scenario works depends on more than its technical correctness. A reader has to be able to follow the events, perceive the educational content as part of the story rather than as something tacked on, and stay involved long enough to reach the end. A short instrument that captures these aspects is useful for early formative evaluation, where response burden has to stay low and full psychometric validation is premature.

2 Methodological framing

Constructs were defined before any item was selected or written. This follows the construct-first approach recommended by Hinkin [6] and Boateng et al. [3] for cases where the target constructs are clearly defined before item writing begins. Seven of the nine items are taken from four instruments with established psychometric records (NES, TS-SF, IMI, MEEGA+), so each adapted item starts from a tested formulation. The pool makes no claim to psychometric validation in its own right. Design choices and their limits are described in Section 8.

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3 Constructs

Narrative clarity refers to how easily a reader can follow the sequence of events and the interaction logic of the scenario. The theoretical anchor is the Narrative Understanding facet of the Narrative Engagement Scale, which targets sense-making and followability of the unfolding story [4].

Story-content coherence captures whether the educational content and the narrative form one structurally integrated whole rather than additive layers. The construct is grounded in the intrinsic-integration principle, under which learning content should be carried by the story's mechanics and choices, not bolted on [5].

Engagement is defined as a combination of perceived enjoyment, narrative curiosity, and focused attention. The construct draws on the Transportation Scale–Short Form, the Intrinsic Motivation Inventory, and MEEGA+ [1, 8, 7].

4 Item generation

With the three constructs above as the working domain, items were drawn from four established host instruments that already cover this domain at the item level. Single items were selected from each instrument rather than carrying the full scale over. This is a deliberate compromise. The pool is intended for short pilots where response burden has to be kept low. Single items serve as candidate indicators of their constructs, not as full-scale measures of a latent dimension. The Engagement subscale in particular is composed formatively, with one item per facet (enjoyment, narrative curiosity, focused attention), and is not assumed to be unidimensional. The selection criterion was face-level fit with the construct definitions in Section 3 and applicability to the IF reception context. Expert ranking of a larger candidate pool was not part of the scope for this pilot instrument.

The Narrative Engagement Scale (NES) supplies items for narrative understanding and narrative realism [4]. The Transportation Scale–Short Form (TS-SF) contributes a curiosity item that maps directly onto narrative engagement [1]. The Intrinsic Motivation Inventory (IMI) contributes a fun/enjoyment item from the Interest/Enjoyment subscale [8]. MEEGA+ contributes items for operability, relevance, and focused attention from its game-evaluation framework [7]. For the coherence construct, two facets had no usable counterpart in any of the host instruments. The corresponding items were written from scratch to reflect the intrinsic-integration principle [5].

Three adaptation steps were applied to each sourced item. First, items were rewritten for the IF reception and decision context. References to “the program”, “the game”, or “the course” were replaced with references to “the story”, “the scenario”, or “the decisions”, depending on which framing fit the construct. Second, reverse-keyed items from the NES were inverted into positively-worded statements so that all items use the same response direction. This is a common compromise in short pilot instruments. It trades a check against acquiescence bias for a faster response task and accepts the slightly higher risk of straight-lining. Third, references to a specific subject matter were replaced with a placeholder. The coherence-fit item contains a parenthetical slot (<topic>) that should be filled in with the actual subject matter of the scenario before the questionnaire is administered. The placeholder makes it explicit that the item refers to a concrete topic, while keeping the instrument reusable across domains.

5 The item pool

Instructions read “Please rate the following statements with regard to the scenario you just played” (“Bitte bewerten Sie die Aussagen bezogen auf das gerade gespielte Szenario.”). All items use a five-

point Likert scale ranging from “strongly disagree” (1) to “strongly agree” (5), localised in administration as “trifft überhaupt nicht zu” to “trifft völlig zu”.

The pool was developed for a German-speaking cohort. The German wordings in Table 1 are the wordings as administered. The English wordings are working translations by the authors. They have not been produced under the back-translation and expert-committee protocol of Beaton et al. [2] and would need a separate translation review before use in an English-language study.

#	English	German	Construct
1	I could easily follow the actions and events in the story.	Ich konnte den Handlungen und Ereignissen in der Geschichte leicht folgen.	Narrative Clarity
2	The interaction rules (how I can make decisions) were clear and easy to understand.	Die Interaktionsregeln (wie ich Entscheidungen treffen kann) waren klar und leicht zu verstehen.	Narrative Clarity
3	The educational content (<topic>) fit well into the story.	Die fachlichen Inhalte (<Themenbereich>) passten gut zur Geschichte.	Coherence
4	The educational content was meaningfully embedded in the plot and the decisions (not merely tacked on).	Die fachlichen Inhalte waren sinnvoll in die Handlung bzw. Entscheidungen eingebettet (nicht nur “drangehängt”).	Coherence
5	It was clear to me how the educational content connects to the story.	Es war mir klar, wie die fachlichen Inhalte mit der Geschichte zusammenhängen.	Coherence
6	The story felt internally logical and convincing.	Die Geschichte wirkte in sich logisch und überzeugend.	Coherence
7	Playing this scenario was fun.	Das Spielen dieses Szenarios hat Spaß gemacht.	Engagement
8	I wanted to know how the story ends.	Ich wollte wissen, wie die Geschichte ausgeht.	Engagement
9	I was so absorbed in the play task that I forgot about the time.	Ich war so in die Spielaufgabe vertieft, dass ich die Zeit vergessen habe.	Engagement

Table 1: The nine Likert items, German wordings as administered, English direct translations, and construct mapping.

6 Item origin

Table 2 traces each item to its source instrument and shows the original wording, so that adaptation steps can be checked directly. For the two coherence items written from scratch, no source wording exists and the table records this explicitly.

7 Pilot scoring

Scoring rules are fixed here before data collection, so that analytic decisions are not shaped by observed pilot distributions. Subscale scores are computed as the arithmetic mean of their items: Narrative Clarity from items 1 and 2, Coherence from items 3 to 6, and Engagement from items 7, 8, and 9. Item-level descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, median, response-category distribution) are reported alongside the subscale means. Internal consistency may be reported per subscale as exploratory information, using Cronbach’s α for the multi-item subscales and the Spearman-Brown coefficient for the two-item Narrative Clarity subscale [6, 3]. The Coherence subscale combines four items from three theoretically distinct sources (two written from scratch for intrinsic integration, one from MEEGA+ Relevance, one paraphrased from NES Narrative Realism). Cronbach’s α here is a descriptive summary of how correlated the items are, not evidence that they measure one underlying dimension. All such values are exploratory descriptors of pilot data, not evidence of measurement quality.

#	Source	Original item or basis
1	NES, Narrative Understanding	"I had a hard time recognizing the thread of the story." (R) [4]
2	MEEGA+, Operability	"The game rules are clear and easy to understand." [7]
3	Theory-derived (intrinsic integration)	No source item. Item written from scratch to reflect the intrinsic-integration principle [5]. Closest neighbour in the host instruments: MEEGA+ Relevance items [7]
4	Theory-derived (intrinsic integration)	No source item. Item written from scratch to express that the educational content is part of the plot and the decisions rather than added on top [5]
5	MEEGA+, Relevance	"It is clear to me how the contents of the game are related to the course." [7]
6	NES, Narrative Realism	Item paraphrased from the Narrative Realism subscale of the NES [4]. Used here as an indicator of perceived internal consistency of the story, not as a measure of realism in the original NES sense
7	IMI, Interest/Enjoyment	"This activity was fun to do." [8]
8	TS-SF, item 3	"I wanted to learn how the narrative ended." [1]
9	MEEGA+, Focused Attention	"I was so involved in my gaming task that I lost track of time." [7]

Table 2: Per-item origin and the original wording or basis used as a starting point.

8 Scope and design choices

The pool has not been validated. Three scope decisions should be made explicit. First, the pool was not reviewed by an expert panel for content validity. For a single-cohort descriptive pilot, item content is grounded in documented origins from validated host instruments (Table 2), so adaptation decisions can be checked directly. An expert-panel review remains a prerequisite before the pool can be developed into a validated scale [6, 3]. Second, no cognitive interviews or pretesting were conducted. How respondents interpret the German wordings, especially of Items 3 to 6 (Coherence) and Item 9 (Focused Attention), is an empirical question left to the first deployment, where item variance and open comments give a first signal. Third, the English wordings are working translations for documentation only. A Beaton-protocol translation [2] would be required before English-language use.

Two further design limits should be flagged. The Coherence subscale combines items from theoretically distinct sources and may not load on a single factor in pilot data. Item 9 ("forgot about the time") targets a flow-adjacent state and is unlikely to discriminate well in short scenarios. For scenarios shorter than roughly twenty minutes, we recommend dropping Item 9 or reporting it separately rather than including it in the Engagement mean.

This note is intended as a supplement to the empirical study in which the pool was first deployed. It reports no data of its own.

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